

CLASSIFICATION OF REFERENCE AND ITS CHARACTERISTICS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20249114>

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada referensiya hodisasi diskurs va matn lingvistikasidagi asosiy kogeziya vositalaridan biri sifatida tadqiq etiladi. Unda anaforik va kataforik referensiya, ularning struktur xususiyatlari hamda matn yaxlitligini ta'minlashdagi o'rni alohida ko'rib chiqiladi. Tadqiqotda M. A. K. Halliday, R. Hasan, I. E. Kim va boshqa olimlar tomonidan ilgari surilgan referensial birliklarning diskursdagi funktsionalligi haqidagi nazariy yondashuvlar tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar. Ekzoforik referensiya, endoforik referensiya, anafora, katafora, shaxs referensiyasi, qiyosiy referensiya, ko'rsatish referensiyasi.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается феномен референции как одного из основных средств когезии в дискурсе и лингвистике текста. Особое внимание уделяется анафорической и катафорической референции, их структурным особенностям и роли в обеспечении связности текста. В исследовании анализируются теоретические подходы, предложенные М. А. К. Halliday, R. Hasan, I. E. Kim и другими учёными, относительно функционирования референциальных единиц в дискурсе.

Ключевые слова. Экзофорическая референция, эндофорическая референция, анафора, катафора, персональная референция, сравнительная референция, указательная референция.

Abstract. This article examines the phenomenon of reference as one of the main cohesive devices in discourse and text linguistics. Particular attention is paid to anaphoric and cataphoric reference, their structural features, and their role in ensuring textual cohesion. The study analyzes the theoretical approaches proposed by M. A. K. Halliday, R. Hasan, I. E. Kim, and other scholars concerning the functioning of referential units in discourse.

Key words. Exophoric reference, endophoric reference, anaphora, cataphora, personal reference, comparative reference, demonstrative reference. ‘

In general linguistics, the concept of reference is regarded as one of the important elements that maintain the coherence and cohesion of a text. Theoretical approaches to this issue are presented in *Cohesion in English*¹⁶ and the following types are identified as: personal reference, comparative reference, demonstrative reference

Scholars: Afriliani A., Cahyati S. S. also use these categories in analyzing their examples and provide following instances for these types:

1) Personal reference. This category includes the pronouns *they, them, he, she, her, his, it, one, and its*. Scholars provide the following example to illustrate this issue:

“Once upon a time there was a prince who wanted to marry a princess, but she would have to be a real princess.”

In this example scholars point out that this example pronoun *she* refers to the princess and it is considered an example of personal reference.

2) Comparative reference. Linguists classify *there, that, this, now*, and the definite article *the* as forms of demonstrative reference, and associate the following example with this type of reference:

¹⁶ Halliday, M. A. K., Hasan, R. *Cohesion in English*. — London: Longman, 1976. — 374 p.

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“One evening a terrible storm came on; there was thunder and lightning, and the rain poured down in torrents¹⁷.”

Here the word *there* is considered as the demonstrative reference.

3) The pronoun *as* is included in this category, as shown in the following example: Nobody but a real princess could be as sensitive as that. From the example, *as sensitive as that* is example of comparing something to other¹⁸.

With regard to the dependence of reference on context and situation, scholars generally classify reference into two major types: external (exophoric) reference and internal (endophoric) reference. In the works of M.A.K. Halliday and Ruqaiya Hasan, these are also referred to as *situational* and *textual* reference respectively.

1) Exophoric reference /situational reference - refers to an object outside the text¹⁹.

Endophoric reference/**textual reference**- refers to an object within the text. Endophoric reference is conventionally subdivided into two principal types: anaphoric reference and cataphoric reference²⁰.

- Anaphoric reference refers to a situation in which the antecedent (the main lexical unit denoting the object) appears first, and then pronouns referring back to it (anaphoric references) follow²¹.

- cataphoric reference is when the pronoun appears first and the antecedent comes later²².

To summarize, this article discussed categories of reference and its mechanisms. The analysis of anaphoric and cataphoric reference demonstrates that referential units play a significant role in connecting textual elements and maintaining semantic continuity. Anaphoric reference, which directs the reader to previously mentioned information, is more frequently used in discourse organization, while cataphoric reference creates anticipation and emphasizes subsequent information within the text.

In addition, based on fundamental works of scholars types of pronouns, which play significant role in referring to its object, were discussed, and as the most important ones: personal, comparative and demonstrative pronouns were researched.

¹⁷ Afriliani, A., Cahyati, S. S. *An analysis of grammatical cohesion of reference in a short story entitled “The Princess and the Pea”* // PROJECT (Professional Journal of English Education). — 2022. — Vol. 5, No. 6. — P. 1144–1149. — DOI: 10.22460/project.v5i6.p1144-1149. — URL: [DOI Article Page](#).

¹⁸ Afriliani, A., Cahyati, S. S. *An analysis of grammatical cohesion of reference in a short story entitled “The Princess and the Pea”* // PROJECT (Professional Journal of English Education). — 2022. — Vol. 5, No. 6. — P. 1144–1149. — DOI: 10.22460/project.v5i6.p1144-1149. — URL: [DOI Article Page](#).

¹⁹ Halliday M. A. K., Hasan R. *Cohesion in English*. — London: Longman, 1976. — P 37-39.

²⁰ Halliday M. A. K., Hasan R. *Cohesion in English*. — London: Longman, 1976. — p 374.

²⁰ Kim, I. E. *Теория референции: учебное пособие: [для студентов бакалавриата по направлению 45.03.03 “Фундаментальная и прикладная лингвистика”]* / I. E. Kim. — Novosibirsk: Publishing and Printing Center of Novosibirsk State University, 2019. — 118 p.

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²¹ Kim, I. E. *Теория референции: учебное пособие: [для студентов бакалавриата по направлению 45.03.03 “Фундаментальная и прикладная лингвистика”]* / I. E. Kim. — Novosibirsk: Publishing and Printing Center of Novosibirsk State University, 2019. — P 44.

²² Halliday, M. A. K., Hasan, R. *Cohesion in English*. — London: Longman, 1976. — P. 56. — URL: [Cohesion in English \(Archive\)](#).

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